

Time management and procrastination during the COVID-19 pandemic in higher education

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ABSTRACT

Online learning is enforced by all higher education in Indonesia due to the COVID-19 pandemic. There is an inability of students to manage time and often delay the work given by the lecturer. This study aimed to reveal the degree of relationship between student time management and academic procrastination in higher education. This research was conducted at the Psychology Faculty of the University Puta Indonesia YPTK Padang, Indonesia. The sample of this research was psychology students as many as 202 respondents. The research instrument was in the form of a questionnaire distributed via Google Form. The results showed that the level of correlation between time management and academic procrastination of psychology students was 0.242 with data processing using SPSS 26. Which means that there is a relationship between students' ability to manage time and delay in completing assignments by students of the faculty of psychology. The role of lecturers in providing direction and motivation to students is very much needed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The application of online learning throughout Indonesia in the field of education began in March 2020 [1]. The online learning policy was delivered by the Indonesian government as an effort to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 in the world of education. Online learning is carried out from home, work in several government offices is also carried out from home, to prevent meeting directly with other people, maintaining distance and minimizing contact with other people [2]. Online learning can be done by utilizing the learning management system (LMS) which is free of charge, making it easier for students and lecturers to pay fees. Because the spread of the COVID-19 can be spread through the touch of a hand, it is limited to direct meetings between students and lecturers or education actors. Sepriana *et al.* [3] said that one way to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 is to carry out activities from home. One of the online learning implemented in higher education at Putra Indonesia University YPTK Padang, Indonesia utilizes the LMS that has been provided by the campus. Online learning carried out by lecturers and students is not easy for students to pass, because there is a time management ability factor by students [4], [5] describes in his research that the ability to manage time affects the work of students. In contrast to what is stated by Pertiwi [6] that between time

arrangements does not have an impact on delaying someone's task. During this COVID-19 pandemic, students experienced serious adaptations in participating in online learning, because they were not used to carrying out full online learning. Reswita [7] in her research stated that between students' ability to manage time is correlated with academic procrastination.

The phenomenon of delaying academic activities that should be done on time is known as procrastination [8]–[10]. Academic procrastination experienced by students if not identified and addressed will have a negative impact on students. Procrastination results in a lot of wasted time, tasks become neglected and when completed the results are not optimal. Academic procrastination is the behavior of procrastinating doing or completing academic tasks [11]. The factor in the occurrence of procrastination by students in online learning with the COVID-19 pandemic condition is due to changes in the learning environment experienced by students [12]. Social situations and tasks that are considered difficult by students are also a factor for students to delay the work assigned by the lecturer [13]. Time management abilities by students need to be investigated, so that students do the tasks given by the lecturer according to the time given. This study aims to provide an overview of academic procrastination experienced by students. Thus, in this era of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is necessary to conduct research related to the ability of students to manage time and its relation to the completion of tasks carried out by students. Many students were found delaying doing assignments sent by lecturers through the LMS used at the Faculty of Psychology, University Putra Indonesia YPTK Padang. Researchers [14], [15] describes in his research that by utilizing the LMS Google Form helps students in submitting assignments online. Melgaard *et al.* [16] said in his research that people who procrastinate on tasks face a higher level of challenge related to learning motivation. Different from what was expressed by Babadoğan [17] that procrastination does not affect student academic achievement. Students' academic procrastination behavior can be reduced by having good learning modalities [17], [18] revealed in their research that delaying doing something by someone is a negative attitude that affects their performance. Online learning is considered ineffective by because many students find procrastination.

Based on the related research that has been described previously, it is important to conduct research that discusses the ability to manage time by students in online learning and the obstacles experienced by students in collecting assignments given by lecturers who are often too late to collect them. This study was conducted with the aim of knowing the correlation between the ability to manage time and the delay in doing assignments by students in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The type of research used is correlational quantitative research, using research methods based on the philosophy of positivism. Namely to examine a particular population or sample, collecting data using research instruments, analyzing quantitative/statistical data, with the aim of testing the established hypothesis [19]. The population in this study were all students of the Faculty of Psychology, University Putra Indonesia YPTK Padang, the sample technique used in this study was a purposive sampling technique, namely students who filled out a questionnaire that had been distributed via a Google Form link. The instrument used in this research is in the form of a questionnaire made using the Google Form application. Table 1 presents the indicator of the instrument from the questionnaire on the variables of time management and academic procrastination [3].

Table 1. Indicator variable time management dan academic procrastination

No	Variabel	Indicator
1	Time Manajemen	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Planning 2. Set priorities 3. Delegate 4. Self disiplin
2	Academic procrastination	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Perceived time, failing to meet deadlines 2. Intention-action, the gap between desire and action 3. Emotional distress, a feeling of anxiety when doing procrastination 4. Perceived ability, or belief in one's ability

Correlation calculations are used to measure the level of relationship between variables. Relationship between independent variable and dependent variable. To calculate the degree of correlation, the Pearson product moment formula is used [20]. The following presents the formula for the Pearson product moment correlation.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{\{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Information:

R_{xy}=one-item correlation coefficient with total items

N=number of respondents

∑X=total score for the perception variable value

∑X²=the sum of the squares of the variable value score perception

∑Y=total score of interest variable value learn

∑Y²=sum of squares of product score score x with a score of y

∑XY=total product of the X and Y scores

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Result

After performing data processing and data analysis using SPSS 26 data processing software, the results and descriptions are obtained in Table 2. In the time management category, the average value is 50.1485 with a standard deviation of 4.46. While in the procrastination category the average was 41.3614 and the standard deviation was 0.015. Table 3. The correlation value between time management and procrastination is 0.242, which means that there is a low correlation between time management and procrastination. If student time management is improved or is in the good category, the delay in doing assignments by students will also be in the low category.

Tabel 2. Descriptive statistics

	Mean	Std. deviation	N
Time management	50.1485	4.46297	202
Procrastination	41.3614	3.15804	202

Tabel 3. Correlations

		Time management	Procrastination
Time management	Pearson correlation	1	.242**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	202	202
Procrastination	Pearson correlation	.242**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	202	202

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

3.2. Discussion

The correlation between time management and academic procrastination was 0.242 which means that there is a positive relationship between students' ability to manage time by delaying doing assignments given by lecturers. That students during online learning do a lot of academic procrastination because they delay assignments in the hope of getting more time to complete academic assignments [21]. In research by Rahimi and Vallerand [21], it was revealed that the COVID-19 pandemic condition was a factor that influenced the delay in carrying out assignments by students in online learning. Online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has had an impact on students in terms of the ability to manage time and delay in doing assignments given by lecturers. Kamaruddin *et al.* [22] revealed in their research that online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on the learning process carried out by teachers and students. Ayeni [23] in his research revealed that managing time in learning is very important for educators to pay attention to so that the goals to be achieved can be realized. The use of social media instgram has a bad impact on students who use it because it causes delays in doing assignments by students, Suárez-Perdomo *et al.* [24] also revealed that the use of social media has an impact on students to delay doing assignments. Meanwhile, the results of other studies reveal that delays in work assignments occur due to poor student motivation and no desire to accept challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic [16]. Anxiety, confusion related to learning are also factors for students to delay doing the assignments given [25], [26] shows that the strategy for adapting online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic must have cooperation with related parties, namely parents, educators, and students. The procrastination experienced by students causes a decrease in student academic achievement [27]. Malatras also revealed that the ability to manage one's own time can have a

positive impact on one's performance [28]. This is closely related to research conducted that between the ability to manage time and delay in doing tasks has a positive correlation. The better the student's ability to manage time, the lower the delay in doing assignments by students. Meanwhile, Maqableh and Alia [29] revealed that a person's ability to manage time contributes to the activities of daily life. Tan and Samavedham [30] found that procrastination by students on an indicator of a person's performance. This shows that students who have good time management skills will have a positive impact on college life, so that procrastination that occurs in online learning can be minimized.

4. CONCLUSION

The conclusion from this research is that time management and academic procrastination variables in online learning have a positive relationship between students' ability to manage time in lectures and students' desire to postpone doing assignments. Students who have the ability to manage time will be low in delaying doing assignments. If University Puta Indonesia YPTK Padang of Psychology Faculty students are given motivation and direction to manage their time well, then delays in working on and completing assignments can be minimized in online learning during this COVID-19 pandemic. The better students' time management, the more likely they are to procrastinate. procrastinating tasks can be lowered. Factors causing academic procrastination include delays in starting and completing assignments by students due to inappropriate timing. Procrastination occurs in students because of student internal factors, such as very low learning motivation, unstable emotional regulation. Thus, there may be internal and external factors that cause delays in online learning.

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